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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

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First progress report on dissemination activities

Submission of Deliverable

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1. Introduction

As the EU-PolarNet *Integrated pan-European communication and engagement delivery plan* states, effective communication is critical for the success of the work of the consortium. The delivery of communication and stakeholder engagement is lead by Work Package 4. Within the work package, primary communication and engagement goals fall into three broad areas:

- **Corporate communication**, which is set to generate a global visibility for EU-PolarNet;
- **Internal communication**, which aims at facilitating an effective interaction between participant institutions and the polar research and operations communities;
- **External communication**, which enables engagement activities with stakeholders, the media and the public.

This progress report on dissemination activities reviews activities of the past 18 months of the project, which targeted both the area of corporate and of external communication. It looks at dissemination activities at conferences and events, online outreach (including the EU-PolarNet website, social media channels and email newsletter), media relations and outreach materials.

2. Dissemination activities at conferences and events

EU-PolarNet consortium members have actively promoted the work of the project at over 40 national, European and international conferences and workshops during the past one and a half years. In addition to presenting the objectives and advances of the consortium at external events, distributing promotional materials and representing the project at panel discussions, members have also organised sessions and Town hall Events at a range of conferences, which were targeted both at a scientific audience and stakeholders.

Events with a EU-PolarNet organised session for example include the 21st Conference of the Parties in Paris, the American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting, the Arctic Frontiers and Adaptation Futures.

The table below lists dissemination activities at conferences and events. A more detailed overview of these activities and events, where EU-PolarNet members have presented the project can be found in the Appendices i1 and i2.

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity
Our Common Future under climate change	07.07.2015	Paris, France	Two sessions were organised: „The Arctic Climate System“ and „Adapting to Arctic Climate Change“
Arctic Circle 2015	16.-18.10.2015	Reykjavik, Iceland	EU-PolarNet and the European Polar Board hosted a session themed "What Can Arctic Stakeholders and Researchers Learn from Each Other?"
COP21	07.12.2015	Paris, France	Joint Side Event themed “Climate Change in the Arctic – Local, Regional and Global Impact” hosted by ICE-ARC, EU-PolarNet and the European Polar Board.
AGU Fall Meeting	14.12.2015	San Francisco, USA	Town Hall Meeting

Arctic Science Summit Week/2 nd EU-PolarNet General Assembly	13.03.2016	Fairbanks, Alaska, USA	Open afternoon session at the 2 nd EU-PolarNet General Assembly
Adaptation Futures	11.05.2016	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	Session themed „The Arctic: Connecting Arctic researchers and industry: a dialogue for societal benefit“
SCAR Open Science Conference	24.08.2016	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Town Hall Meeting
EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event	27.09.2016	Brussels, Belgium	Town Hall “Towards the 1.5°C climate goal. Perspectives from the Polar Regions”.

3. Online outreach

3.1. The EU-PolarNet Website

The EU-PolarNet website (www.eu-polarnet.eu) was officially launched on 19th May 2015. It functions as one of the main online dissemination platforms for raising awareness about the project, sharing information related to the work of the consortium or affiliated projects and cooperation partners, and promoting upcoming events. The targeted audience ranges from the general public, to national and international policy makers, representatives from the industry, NGOs, interest groups and the wider science community. To meet the interest and needs of the various audience segments, the website offers both a wide range of informational static content and regularly updated contents, such as announcements and news.

The website furthermore hosted a public consultation on European research objectives in polar research (<http://www.eu-polarnet.eu/project-themes/polar-research-for-science-and-society/public-consultation-on-research-priorities/>). The survey enabled members of the wider science community and interested non-academic stakeholders to comment on and contribute to a compilation of European polar research priorities.

The website also contains an internal part, which consortium members can log into, in order to retrieve consortium internal information and documents.

3.2. The EU-PolarNet Social Media Presences

EU-PolarNet has four social media presences:

- [Facebook public group](#) with ca. 300 members.
- [Twitter channel](#) (@EUPolarNet) with ca. 500 followers.
- [LinkedIn group](#) with 65 members.
- [Youtube channel](#) presenting 16 interviews with EU-PolarNet consortium members.

The main objective of the social media channels is firstly to engage with the wider science community and stakeholders on a regular and immediate basis. Secondly, the channels allow consortium members to post and tweet content, while the YouTube channel features interviews with the members – thereby giving EU-PolarNet a face.

3.3. The EU-PolarNet Newsletter

Since November 2015, a quarterly EU-PolarNet newsletter informs recipients about news from the consortium and affiliated projects, reflects on developments in European polar research, introduces individual European polar research communities and gives a glimpse of conferences and events coming up in near future. So far three issues have been sent out to around 300 recipients.

4. Media relations

At the launch of EU-PolarNet and before the major EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event in Brussels press releases were sent out to international and national media contacts, translating the text to the respective member's country's language and informing about the emerging work of the consortium. Since then EU-PolarNet has been approached by various media outlets, resulting in a range of articles and a feature by Euronews (see Appendix ii).

5. Outreach Materials

The BAS media team has created a range of outreach materials, including an EU-PolarNet flyer, a roll-up and a poster, which have been distributed and set up during various conferences and workshops. Furthermore for the EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event in Brussels, USB-Hubs were created, which carried the slogan "Connecting Science with Society".

APPENDIX

i. Details about dissemination activities at conferences

i.1. EU-PolarNet organised sessions and workshops

Type of activity	Two sessions
Name of the event (in English)	Our Common Future under climate change
Date	07/07/2015 and 07/07/2015
Location	Paris, France
Link to event website if available	http://www.commonfuture-paris2015.org/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	<p>The conference was the largest forum for the scientific community to come together ahead of the 21st UNFCCC Conference of the Parties (COP21). Building on the results of IPCC 5th Assessment Report (AR5), the Conference addressed key issues concerning climate change in the broader context of global change. It offered an opportunity to discuss solutions for both mitigation and adaptation issues. For EU-PolarNet the conference was a chance to emphasize the importance of the Polar Regions for the global climate.</p> <p>Session 1112: The Arctic Climate System Session 3327: Adapting to Arctic Climate Change</p>
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	<p>Denis-Didier Rousseau (CNRS) – session chair Kirsi Latola (Oulu) – session chair Nicole Biebow (AWI) – keynote speaker</p>
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	<p>Anders Oskal, Director at International Centre on Reindeer Husbandry, during this key note speech (Photo: Kirsi Latola)</p>
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Session
Name of the event (in English)	Arctic Circle
Date	16/10/2015 and 18/10/2015
Location	Reykjavik, Iceland
Link to event website if available	http://www.arcticcircle.org/assemblies/2015
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	<p>The Arctic Circle is the largest network of international dialogue and cooperation on the future of the Arctic. It is an open democratic platform with participation from governments, organizations, corporations, universities, think tanks, environmental associations, indigenous communities, concerned citizens, and others interested in the development of the Arctic and its consequences for the future of the globe.</p> <p>EU-PolarNet and the European Polar Board hosted a session at the Arctic Circle 2015: "What Can Arctic Stakeholders and Researchers Learn from Each Other?"</p>
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) –speaker Karin Lochte (AWI) – panellist Yves Frenot (IPEV) – panellist Kirsi Latola (Oulu) – panellist Renuka Badhe (EPB) - panellist
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	<p>The panellists at the EU-PolarNet session (f.l.t.r.: Karin Lochte (AWI), Jeremy Wilkinson (BAS), Yves Frenot (IPEV), Kiris Latola (Oulu), Volker Rachold (IASC), Renuka Badhe (EPB))</p>
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Side Event
Name of the event (in English)	21st Conference of the Parties, Paris
Date	07/12/2015
Location	Paris, France
Link to event website if available	http://unfccc.int/meetings/paris_nov_2015/meeting/8926/php/view/seors.php
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	This joint Side Event themed “Climate Change in the Arctic – Local, Regional and Global Impact” hosted by ICE-ARC, EU-PolarNet and the European Polar Board provided high-level decision-makers and other interested parties with a holistic overview of Arctic change and its multi-sector impacts (climatic, societal, and economic) at local, regional and global levels. A flow of up-to-date information from leaders in their field was given followed by an open discussion. This Side Event provided an excellent opportunity to discuss with the experts, advanced knowledge that is needed for effective and evidence-based decision-making.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Heather Martin (BAS) – organiser Denis-Didier Rousseau (CNRS) – official EU-PolarNet representative Renuka Badhe (EPB) – organiser
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	<p>Speakers and organisers (f.l.t.r.: Denis-Didier Rousseau (CNRS), Sheila Watt-Cloutier, Thorben Hoffmeister, Anthony Hobley, Sir David King, Jean-Claude Gascard, Renuka Badhe (EPB), Jeremy Wilkinson (BAS)) (Photo: Heather Martin, BAS)</p>
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Town hall
Name of the event (in English)	AGU Fall Meeting
Date	14/12/2015
Location	San Francisco, USA
Link to event website if available	http://fallmeeting.agu.org/2015/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	The AGU Fall Meeting brought together the entire Earth and space sciences community for discussions of emerging trends and the latest research. The technical program included presentations on new and cutting-edge science, much of which has not yet been published.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – speaker/Townhall convener Renuka Badhe (EPB) – Townhall convener
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Open session
Name of the event (in English)	2nd EU-PolarNet General Assembly (during Arctic Science Summit Week 2016)
Date	13/03/2016
Location	Fairbanks (Alaska), USA
Link to event website if available	http://assw2016.org/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Anyone interested in the work of EU-PolarNet and eager to join a discussion on the project's future tasks and expectations was welcome to the open afternoon session of the 2 nd EU-PolarNet General Assembly. A special focus of the meeting was on the project's stakeholder mapping, the development of a coordinated European Polar Data Infrastructure and the identification of research priorities for European polar science.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Representatives from all EU-PolarNet partner organisations
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	<p>Participants of the open afternoon session of the second EU-PolarNet General Assembly (Photo: Kristina Bär, AWI)</p>
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Session
Name of the event (in English)	Adaptation Futures
Date	11/05/2016
Location	Rotterdam, The Netherlands
Link to event website if available	http://www.adaptationfutures2016.org/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Adaptation Futures is the biennial conference of the Global Programme of Research on Climate Change Vulnerability, Impacts and Adaptation, which took place 10th to 13th May 2016 in Rotterdam, the Netherlands. Set out to engage scientists, practitioners, policymakers and business people from all around the world, the conference offered a good opportunity for EU-PolarNet to engage with various stakeholders, especially industry representatives. The aim of the project's session was to improve mutually beneficial engagement and interaction between EU-PolarNet participants and stakeholders from industry, the international research community, as well as the wider society, including young people.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – organiser/speaker Annette Scheepstra (RUG) – organiser Kirsi Latola (Oulu) – organiser Hannele Savela (Oulu) – organiser Renuka Badhe (EPB) - organiser
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Townhall
Name of the event (in English)	SCAR Open Science Conference
Date	24/08/2016
Location	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Link to event website if available	http://scar2016.com/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	The SCAR Open Science conference 2016 will focus on Antarctica in the Global Earth System: From the Poles to the Tropics and how the changes that we are currently seeing in Antarctica will affect the rest of the world. The conference offers a good opportunity for EU-PolarNet to liaise with the Antarctic research community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – organiser/speaker Renuka Badhe (EPB) - organiser
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Town Hall
Name of the event (in English)	“Towards the 1.5°C climate goal. Perspectives from the Polar Regions”.
Date	27/09/2016
Location	Brussels, Belgium
Link to event website if available	http://www.eu-polarnet.eu/news-and-events/conferences-and-workshops/eu-polarnet-townhall-event-2016/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	The objective of the event was to stimulate a dialogue between international and national policy makers, polar scientists, industries, local communities and civil society to explore how future polar research can contribute to the “1.5°C target” agreed at the 21 st Conference of the Parties in Paris.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Entire consortium
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers, roll-up, USB Hubs
Images	<p>Participants of the EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event in Brussels. (c) RBINS - Th. Hubin</p>
Other relevant information	n/a

i.2. Presentation of EU-PolarNet at conferences and workshops

Type of activity	Poster presentation
Name of the event (in English)	IAATO Meeting
Date	30/04/2015
Location	Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility in the polar community, with IAATO being an important key stakeholder for the project.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Annette Scheepstra (RUG) – poster presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers and poster
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presentation
Name of the event (in English)	What's next for Arctic policy
Date	01/06/2015 – 02/06/2015
Location	Brussels, Belgium
Link to event website if available	http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/fpi/showcases/eu_arctic_policy_en.htm
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	On 1-2 June, the European External Action Service in cooperation with the European Commission hosted a consultation event on the EU's future Arctic policy. Nearly 140 high-level and influential speakers and participants from academia and research, local, regional, national and international politics, the business sector and non-governmental organisations were in attendance.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – speaker
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presentation of Information Paper
Name of the event (in English)	Antarctic Treaty Consultative Meeting (ATCM)
Date	01/06/2015 – 10/06/2015
Location	Sofia, Bulgaria
Link to event website if available	n/a
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Information about EU-PolarNet was presented as an Information Paper in the meeting. The paper was presented by Germany, and supported by, Belgium, Bulgaria, France, and Portugal. The IP was well received, with Delegates requesting further information after the presentation. This was provided by R Badhe as necessary.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Renuka Badhe (EPB) – delegate
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	n/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presentation
Name of the event (in English)	Year of Polar Predictions Summit
Date	13/07/2015 – 15/07/2015
Location	Geneva, Switzerland
Link to event website if available	n/a
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Statement of support by EU-PolarNet.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – speaker
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presentation
Name of the event (in English)	COMNAP Antarctic Roadmap Challenges
Date	23/08/2015 – 25/08/2015
Location	Tromsø, Norway
Link to event website if available	n/a
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Liaising with the Antarctic community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – speaker
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presenter
Name of the event (in English)	Arctic Dialogue
Date	01/09/2015
Location	Berlin, Germany
Link to event website if available	http://www.awi.de/en/about-us/network/arctic-dialog.html
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst German policy makers.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers and poster
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presenter
Name of the event (in English)	Lynet Board Meeting
Date	01/10/2015
Location	Oulu, Finland
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst the Finnish national science community and policy makers.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Kirsi Latola (Oulu) – presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presenter
Name of the event (in English)	Dutch National Polar Symposium
Date	05/11/2015
Location	The Hague, The Netherlands
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst the Dutch national polar community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Annette Scheepstra (RUG) –presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	n/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presenter
Name of the event (in English)	APECS-NL
Date	06/11/2015
Location	The Hague, The Netherlands
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst the young Dutch national polar community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Annette Scheepstra (RUG) – presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	n/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presenter
Name of the event (in English)	Les Fondamentales du CNRS
Date	13/11/2015
Location	Paris, France
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst the national French science community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Denis-Didier Rousseau (CNRS) –presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	n/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Presenter
Name of the event (in English)	Central Europe Polar Meeting
Date	11/11/2015
Location	Vienna, Austria
Link to event website if available	http://www.polarresearch.at/1st-central-european-polar-meeting/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst the Central European polar community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Annette Scheepstra (RUG) – presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	n/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Planery talk
Name of the event (in English)	ArcticNet
Date	07/12/2015
Location	Vancouver, Canada
Link to event website if available	n/a
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Liaising with the Canadian Polar Research Community.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – speaker Renuka Badhe (EPB) – participant
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Plenary talk
Name of the event (in English)	Finnish Round Table in the French Embassy
Date	10/12/2015
Location	Helsinki, Finland
Link to event website if available	n/a
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Raising the EU-PolarNet visibility amongst the Finnish science community and policy makers.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Denis-Didier Rousseau (CNRS) - presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	N/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Panel/Stall
Name of the event (in English)	Arctic Frontiers
Date	25/01/2016 – 28/01/2016
Location	Tromsø, Norway
Link to event website if available	http://www.arcticfrontiers.com/downloads/arctic-frontiers-2016
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	EU-PolarNet's project manager, Nicole Biebow (AWI), joined the panel for this year's Arctic Frontiers breakout session on 'Arctic Visions' and was asked to share a European research view.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI) – panellist Kristina Bär (AW) – participant
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet flyers
Images	<p>Nicole Biebow (AWI) representing a shared European research view. (Photo: Kristina Bär, AWI)</p>
Other relevant information	n/a

Type of activity	Plenary Lecture
Name of the event (in English)	36th Polish Polar Symposium
Date	09/06/2016 – 10/06/2016
Location	Lublin, Poland
Link to event website if available	n/a
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	Information about EU-PolarNet was presented as a part of an invited Plenary lecture in the meeting.
EU-PolarNet Participants at the event and their role	Renuka Badhe (EPB) – presenter
EU-PolarNet materials displayed/distributed	n/a
Images	n/a
Other relevant information	n/a

ii. Press Hits

May 2015

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